

Appropriation of the Territory and Active Learning through Environmental Interpretation Walks at the National University of Colombia, Bogotá Campus

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Abstract

Environmental interpretation tours are spaces that allow the university community to have a direct approach with open ecosystems of active learning and innovation, operating under the conditions and complexities inherent to real life. In this way, individuals within a community not only observe but also participate in all the processes taking place there, from the development of ideas to the implementation of experiments. In the implementation strategy of environmental tours, pedagogical actions will be developed in various environmental themes, with three lines of deepening: comprehensive waste management, fauna, and tree cover. Through the sustainability education and culture program, individuals enjoy and immerse themselves in nature, fauna, and flora through walks and passive recreational activities, without having to travel more than fifteen minutes walking within the walls of the concrete jungle, Bogotá. There they will find savannah snakes, beautiful trees providing a refreshing climate, and the peace and tranquility that nature offers. At the same time, this will generate recognition of different strategic ecosystems, providing sustenance, provision, regulation, and cultural services. By directly experiencing and interacting with them, the community can reflect, acquire knowledge, and understanding through activities facilitating the appropriation of the territory for its use, conservation, and restoration of the university campus. These tours are aimed at an open audience, fostering knowledge, exploration, and dissemination of places with environmental interest. Additionally, they are an open space for environmental volunteering, supporting Environmental School Projects and training processes, which can be developed with all age groups: children, youth, adults, and seniors who are part of the university community.

Keywords: Active Learning; Environmental interpretation; Strategic ecosystems; University environmental responsibility; Sustainability; Appropriation of the territory.

1 Introduction

Environmental tours are constituted as open ecosystems of learning and innovation, where active participation in all processes reflects the conditions and complexities of real life. In this environment, the community not only observes but also participates from the development of the idea to the execution of experiments. This integral approach is integrated into the strategy of environmental tours, which seeks to promote pedagogical actions in various environmental themes, deepening in three lines from the Education for Sustainability program. One of these lines of action focuses on education and University Environmental Responsibility in the cultural appropriation of sustainability. Here, the aim is to incorporate environmental and sustainability themes into the institutional educational practice through university social responsibility. This involves a commitment to the integral formation of all university actors, from students to administrative staff, in the development of competencies and ethical values in relation to society and the environment.

Environmental interpretation tours are a key tool in this strategy, to foster knowledge, exploration, and dissemination of places with environmental interest. These tours not only provide information about the natural environment but also serve as open spaces for environmental volunteering, support for academic environmental projects, and training processes for all age groups of the university community. Furthermore,

for participants to make sense of the information and connect new ideas with their previous knowledge, an active learning approach is required. This process involves reflection, practice, and application of new knowledge and skills to develop a deep and lasting understanding. In contrast to the passive approach, active learning fosters the connection of ideas and creative thinking, fundamental elements in the formation of citizens committed to sustainability (Cortes Mora, University Social Responsibility: A Look at the National University of Colombia, 2012). In this article, we will explore how the integration of environmental tours and the active learning approach contribute to participatory and meaningful environmental education in the university setting.

Figure 1. Image of first semester students on an environmental interpretation tour

2 Scope

The scope of this study will encompass a detailed exploration of how the integration of environmental tours and active learning approaches contribute to participatory and meaningful environmental education in the university setting. The conceptualization of environmental tours as open ecosystems of learning and innovation will be examined, where participation reflects the cultural appropriation of University Environmental Responsibility.

This includes the incorporation of environmental and sustainability themes into the institution's educational practice through university environmental responsibility. Additionally, the fundamental role of environmental interpretation tours as a key tool in this strategy will be examined, with a focus on active learning, necessary for the community to make sense of information and connect new ideas with their previous knowledge, contributing to the development of a deep and lasting understanding (Education, Cambridge Assessment International, 2019). The aim is to understand how this approach fosters the connection of ideas and creative thinking in the formation of citizens committed to sustainability.

3 Methodology

The methodology employed in this study focuses on the development and implementation of the Education and Culture Plan for Sustainability, aiming to address the environmental issues presented and improve the

environmental conditions at the Bogotá campus. This plan aims to formulate new programs and enhance existing ones to enhance human well-being and promote greater university environmental responsibility for the preservation and conservation of the environment on campus and in daily life. It is important to highlight that this educational plan aligns with other guidelines produced by the National Project for Excellence in Environmental Education of the North American Association for Environmental Education, (Ariza & Rueda Toncel, 2016) serving as an integrated sequence of experiences and educational materials designed to achieve specific objectives according to the needs of each institution.

The plan's implementation is carried out through five programs, each with multiple activities that will be conducted both virtually and in person to raise awareness and promote knowledge on environmental issues, covering legislative, procedural, anthropic, and natural components (Yañez, 2021). These activities are designed to provide comprehensive, formal, and non-formal education, allowing the university community to acquire information and knowledge to build sustainable environmental knowledge, values, and practices.

Figure 2. High school students participating in a social cartography activity during an environmental tour

This experience is based on the second line of action of the Education and Culture Plan for Sustainability, namely, Education and University Environmental Responsibility in the cultural appropriation of sustainability, which includes the Environmental Tours strategy with a pilot program consisting of four tours, two natural and two anthropic. These tours are conducted through guided visits around the Bogotá campus, identifying areas of environmental, cultural, historical, and heritage significance, as well as environmental management practices on campus. The tours are available to the university community and various interest groups, such as schools, universities, and the surrounding community, and are conducted during daylight hours. Additionally, requests can be made to the environmental management office to open spaces for these tours during university events or activities. Each tour lasts approximately two hours, during which strategic stops are made to share information and knowledge about environmentally significant areas on campus. Additionally, more specific and complementary activities are conducted, such as observation races and fauna identification events like BioBlitz, (National geographic learning, 2019) where birds are observed and different species of fauna, flora, and trees are identified along with experts in participatory citizen science events.

Promoting learning and autonomy among participants opens up the possibility of becoming more involved in the learning process and having greater control over what they learn, providing them with the necessary skills to promote active learning and develop metacognitive thinking. In this context, various factors come into play, such as the social context, which constitutes a powerful set of forces that influence education, including

considerations of ethics, social justice, worldview, freedoms, authorities, power, among others. Within this social context, significant attention is deserved by the governing officials, as elements of social control, who are immersed in these spaces where people from diverse social groups participate and share their different reflections during these events, allowing for the analysis of environmental contexts from different perspectives.

4 Results

Within the evidenced results of the impacts and benefits that would arise from the implementation of the Education and Culture Plan for Sustainability at the Bogotá campus, specifically for the environmental tours program, some projected outcomes could include:

- Promoting cultural appropriation in university environmental responsibility: It is expected that carrying out activities such as environmental tours will improve environmental responsibility among members of the university community and other stakeholders, gaining firsthand knowledge of the reality of ecosystems, observing animals, from snakes, birds, and others, that allow attendees to transform their perception about the importance of preserving ecosystems, where at the end of the tours we create spaces for reflection and as a common denominator the community refers to a before and after regarding the perception of their ecosystems.
- Change in environmental practices: Participation in programs and activities related to environmental education is expected to equip participants with knowledge and skills to adopt more sustainable practices in their daily lives and on campus, through active learning, allowing participants to connect with their environment, enabling two elements to mutually enhance each other, providing significant benefits for the physical, cognitive, and emotional development of individuals.
- Development of sustainable skills and values: Participation in formal and informal educational activities will allow participants to acquire knowledge, skills, and values related to sustainability that they can apply in their personal and professional lives, as these tours can show, for example, in the waste collection points, the amount of waste generated by the community, and highlight the work of the center's operators, carrying out waste separation, generating reflections in the participants about the impact, inadequate management, and labor re-signification, as an example of some spaces visited during the tours.
- The impact on the surrounding community: The availability of environmental tours and other activities for the university community and external groups can have a positive impact on the surrounding community by increasing environmental awareness, promoting sustainable practices, and allowing the participation of different social groups and stakeholders that enable the contraction of new knowledge, reflection of ideas, and construction of new knowledge among the participants.

5 Discussion

In the discussion of the results obtained from the implementation of the Education and Culture Plan for Sustainability on the Bogotá campus, it is crucial to highlight several key points. Firstly, it is observed that engaging in activities such as environmental tours has had a significant impact on environmental awareness and the promotion of environmental responsibility among university students and other stakeholders. This is evidenced by increased participation in environmental education programs and changes in environmental practices both on campus and in participants' daily lives.

Furthermore, it is noted that the integration of active learning into the plan has significantly contributed to strengthening the university community's commitment to environmental protection. The opportunity to actively participate in the learning process has allowed students to develop practical skills applicable to their daily lives, leading to greater reflection on their role in environmental preservation and the adoption of concrete measures to promote positive change.

Additionally, the positive impact of these educational activities on the surrounding community is emphasized. The availability of environmental tours and other activities has increased environmental awareness in the community and promoted more sustainable practices overall.

In summary, the results of this study suggest that the implementation of the Education and Culture Plan for Sustainability has been effective in promoting greater environmental awareness, fostering environmental responsibility, and strengthening the university community's commitment to environmental protection. The integration of active learning into the plan has been key to achieving these results, providing participants with the opportunity to actively engage in the learning process and develop skills and values related to sustainability

6 Conclusion

The implementation of the Education and Culture Plan for Sustainability on the Bogotá campus offers a series of significant impacts and benefits for both the university community and society at large. Through programs such as environmental tours, the aim is not only to promote greater environmental awareness and foster environmental responsibility among university members and other interest groups, but also to promote active learning.

Participation in sustainability-related educational activities provides participants with the opportunity to actively engage in the learning process, allowing them to develop practical and applicable skills in their daily lives. In addition to acquiring knowledge and skills related to sustainability, participants also have the opportunity to reflect on their role in preserving the environment and to take concrete actions to promote positive change.

By integrating active learning into the Education and Culture Plan for Sustainability, the commitment of the university community to environmental protection is further strengthened, and a deeper and more ingrained culture of environmental stewardship is fostered. This approach not only benefits the university and its members, but also has a positive impact on the surrounding community by increasing environmental responsibility and promoting more sustainable practices overall.

In summary, the Education and Culture Plan for Sustainability represents an important step towards building a greener, more responsible university environment committed to preserving the environment and the well-being of future generations, while also promoting active learning and the university community's commitment to environmental sustainability.

7 References

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